

OUT-OF-PLANE TENSILE MODULUS OF UD-CFRP LAMINATE BY 3-POINT BENDING TEST

E. Hara^{1*}, T. Yokozeki², Y. Iwahori¹, H. Hatta³, T. Ishikawa⁴
¹ IAT, JAXA, Tokyo, Japan, ² University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan,
³ ISAS, JAXA, Kanagawa, Japan, ⁴ Nagoya University, Aichi, Japan,
 * Corresponding author (eichi12@chofu.jaxa.jp)

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Abstract

In order to propose a test method for the out-of-plane tensile modulus of laminated Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs), 3-point bending tests using a laminated CFRP with the a span direction coinciding with out-of-plane (through-the-thickness) direction were performed (Fig.1). It was demonstrated that apparent bending modulus depends on the Length of span to thickness ratio (L/t) and tensile modulus E to shear modulus G ratio (E/G). Sensitivity analysis was performed in order to select a Length of span to thickness ratio (L/t) for evaluating bending modulus near material modulus. As a results, It is predicted that bending modulus performed with an $L/t > 25$ bending specimen is equivalent to tensile modulus, if the apparent bending modulus were evaluated from 1 GPa to 15 GPa.

1 Introduction

In the latest commercial aircraft, composites are used in major structural parts. It is important for characterization to evaluate not only in-plane properties but also out-of-plane properties. In response to these concerns, a direct out-of-plane tensile test method (ASTM D 7291 [1]) for CFRP laminates was standardized by ASTM. Fig.2 and Fig.3 shows test setup for direct loading test. However, this test method has several problems. Regulation for calculating the out-of-plane modulus involved the use of strains measured by strain gages on the side of the cylindrical specimen: either two gages separated by 180 degrees or three strain gages 120 degrees apart (Fig.4). However this method is not sufficient to evaluate out-of-plane tensile modulus. The out-of-plane strain of anisotropic material also varies with specimen thickness, diameter and measuring position under the condition of ASTM D 7291 (Fig.5, 6) [2].

Fig.1 Test setup for 3-point bending test.

Fig.2 Test setup for direct loading test (cylindrical specimen).

Fig.6 shows the distribution of tensile strain ε_z of the UD-CFRP along the line on which the mid-plane and the side-surface intersect under average tensile stresses σ_z of 5, 15, and 30 MPa [2]. The marked data points in this figure represent ε_z observed using strain gages 2 mm long, and the horizontal axis shows the measuring position, where θ was set to be 0° when the direction combining the origin and side surface coincides with the fiber axis. As this figure shows, ε_z varies with θ . The curves in the figure are the result of FEA calculations. The curves are consistent with the experimental values, showing that tensile load was appropriately applied to the specimens in the present tests.

Fig.7 shows measured apparent out-of-plane moduli of UD-CFRP determined at 0° , 45° , and 90° positions as a function of direct loading test specimen thickness t_{dl} . The symbols represent experimentally determined values of moduli, and the curves calculated results of FEA. When $t = 50$ mm, out-of-plane modulus is approximately 8.21 GPa, which coincides with the reference value shown in Table 1. However, measured apparent out-of-plane modulus increases with decreasing specimen thickness t_{dl} to arrive at approximately 16 GPa at t_{dl} less than 10 mm when the measuring position is 90° . This tendency indicates that a thicker specimen is

preferable for the determination of out-of-plane tensile modulus by the direct loading method.

Consequently, the evaluated out-of-plane modulus varies with these parameters. Thus authors reported problems, solutions, and an alternative solution to this test method; concerning not only modulus but also strength [2, 3, and 4].

Fig. 3 Test setup for direct loading test (cylindrical specimen).

Fig.4 Strain measurement positions. The positions are recommended by ASTM D 7291.

Fig.5 Definitions of coordinate systems [1, 2, and 3], and mid-plane. Direction [1] is in-plane fiber direction. Depiction of the relation between the fiber direction and positions for 0° and 90° strain measurement positions.

Fig.6 Distributions of tensile strain ϵ_z on a cylindrical specimen made of 12 mm thickness UD-CFRP along the periphery on the mid-plane, under the indicated uniform loads where measurement position shows the angle to the fiber orientation θ . The curves represent calculated results using the finite element method.

Fig.7 Apparent out-of-plane moduli measured by direct loading test specimen using unidirectional reinforced composite measured at 0° , 45° , and 90° positions as functions of specimen thickness t_{dl} . The solid curves were calculated by finite element analysis.

Table 1 Moduli and Poisson's ratios of UD-CFRP(IM600/#133) lamina for FEA.

Property		unit	Test method
E_1	152	G Pa	SACMA SRM 4R[5]
E_2	8.21	G Pa	SACMA SRM 4R
G_{12}	4.36[6]	G Pa	SACMA SRM 7R[7]
ν_{12}	0.334	-	SACMA SRM 4R
E_3	8.21	G Pa	assumption: $E_3=E_2$
G_{13}	3.993	G Pa	ASTM D 5379[8]
G_{23}	2.516	G Pa	ASTM D 5379
ν_{13}	0.346	-	SACMA SRM 4R
ν_{23}	0.536	-	SACMA SRM 4R

It is reported that in-plane tensile modulus could be evaluated from an in-plane bending test, comparing with moduli from tensile test and bending test [9]. We supposed that similar methods could be applied for the out-of-plane tensile property. The purpose of this study is to propose and demonstrate bending tests varies the L/t ratio about UD-CFRP for discussion about conditions enough to evaluate out-of-plane tensile modulus accurately.

2. Relationship between bending and tensile moduli

The apparent bending modulus using 3-point bending tests varies according to an L/t ratio. The reason for this variation is the fact that the total beam deflection of the centerline is the sum of the shear and bending deflection in a centrally loaded bending test specimen. Fig.8 shows illustrations of bending and shear beam deformation. Zweben et al. showed equation (1) as apparent bending modulus E_b by 3-point bending tests [9].

$$E_b = \frac{PL^3}{4wt^3 \Delta_b (1 + \Delta_s / \Delta_b)}, \quad (1)$$

Where Δ_s is Shear deflection in a centrally loaded bending test specimen and Δ_b is bending deflection in a centrally loaded bending test specimen. Δ_s is given by equation (2) and Δ_b by equation (3):

$$\Delta_s = \frac{0.3PL}{Gwt} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta_b = \frac{1}{4} \frac{PL^3}{Ewt^3} \quad (3)$$

The apparent bending modulus is close to tensile modulus provided that the ratio Δ_s / Δ_b is sufficiently small because the reduction Δ_s / Δ_b causes a reduction in the effect imposed on bending modulus by the shear component. Equation (4) shows the ratio of Δ_s / Δ_b .

$$\frac{\Delta_s}{\Delta_b} = 1.2 \left(\frac{E}{G} \right) \left(\frac{1}{L/t} \right)^2. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the measured bending modulus is an apparent modulus dependent on ratios E/G and L/t .

Fig.8(a) Shear deformation Δ_s

Fig.8(b) Bending deformation Δ_b

3. Experiments

A UD-CFRP was chosen as materials. These CFRPs were fabricated from a unidirectionally reinforced prepreg made of reinforcing fiber IM600 and epoxy matrix #133. A nominal ply thickness was 0.145mm. CFRP plates were fabricated by laminating 200 plies of prepreg sheets and curing them at 180°C. The resulting UD-CFRP plate was 29 mm thick, while the stacking sequences was $[0]_{200}$. Fig. 9 shows UD-CFRP plate, bending specimen and direct loading test spool specimen.

All specimens were machined from the mother plate. As shown in Fig.10, bending specimens were machined ensuring that the thickness direction of the mother plate coincided with that of the span. Table 2 shows the configurations of specimens. 3-point bending tests were carried out based on ASTM D 790[10].

Fig.9 The relationship of machining locations among bending, direct loading test specimens (cylindrical specimen) and mother plate

Fig.10 Mother plate and bending specimen.

The radius of the loading nose was 5mm and the radius of support noses 2mm (Fig.1). Total beam deflection of the centerline D was measured. Bending strain ε_b and bending stress σ_b were calculated from equations (5) and (6), respectively.

$$\varepsilon_b = \frac{6Dt}{L^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3PL}{2wt^2} \quad (6)$$

Table 2 Configurations of bending test

#	Length of span	Thickness	Length of span to thickness ratio
	L	t	L/t
	mm	mm	-
1	7.5	1.0	7.5
2	7.5	0.5	15
3	15	1.0	15
4	25	1.0	25
5	15	0.5	30
6	25	0.5	50

4. Sensitivity analysis

The relationship between ratios E_b/E and L/t was discussed. In this sensitivity analysis, material models were calculated as homogeneous material. According to a strictly definition, bending specimens in this study were heterogeneous material because of laminate structure of CFRP. However, effect of laminate structure was ignored in this study because stacking sequence of specimen was uni-directional. E_b/E is a ratio for normalized apparent bending modulus E_b in tensile modulus E . Fig.11 shows the modulus ratio as a function of L/t and tensile modulus E under the condition of constant shear modulus G : 2.5 GPa. Fig.12 shows the modulus ratio as a function of L/t and shear modulus G under the condition of constant tensile modulus E : 10 GPa.

Fig.11 The modulus ratio as a function of Length of span to thickness ratio (L/t) under the condition of constant shear modulus G .

Fig.12 The modulus ratio as a function of Length of span to thickness ratio (L/t) under the condition of constant tensile modulus E .

As shown in Fig.11, E_b/E exceeds 98% under conditions of L/t : 25 and tensile modulus E : 5 ~15 GPa. As shown in Fig. 12, apparent bending modulus E_b is close to tensile modulus E under relatively low L/t provided that shear modulus G increases. E_b/E exceeds 97% under $L/t > 25$ even though the predicted curve of the shear modulus G : 1GPa is assumed as low shear modulus. The shear modulus G of almost of neat epoxy resin exceeded 1GPa. Moreover, the shear modulus G of FRP exceeded 1Gpa, because the shear modulus of FRP exceeded neat resin. Therefore, consideration of shear modulus of UD-CFRP is not required, assuming that resin in FRP has tensile and shear modulus in this paper, and L/t were at least 25.

Based on the above discussions, it is predicted that an apparent bending modulus under 15 GPa could be regarded as tensile modulus if measured with an $L/t > 25$ bending specimen.

5. Experimental results

Fig. 1 shows the set-up for the bending test. And Fig. 13, Fig.14 and Fig.15 shows the stress-strain curves of UD-CFRP obtained by a bending test under the condition $L25mm/t1mm$, $L15mm/t0.5mm$, and $L25mm/t0.5mm$, respectively. The apparent bending moduli were calculated with a stress-strain slope with fracture stress of between 25 and 50%.

Fig.16 shows the bending modulus of UD-CFRP as a function of L/t . A bending modulus vs. L/t curve predicted with equation (1) was also shown in Fig.16. The shear modulus G for prediction was used as shear modulus G : 2.5GPa. Predicted curves under 8.1 and 8.7GPa were also shown in Fig.16; assuming the error of the measured modulus to be 0.3GPa.

6. Discussion

Experimental moduli by 3-point bending tests under the condition of $L/t > 25$, were consistent to in-plane transverse modulus E_2 in Table 1. The consistent in both moduli is reasonable if the relationship between out-of-plane and in-plane transverse direction is taken into consideration.

The 3-point bending test has the following merits:

- (1) Low cost for machining specimens due to the simple specimen geometry,
- (2) Test can be easily and generally performed, and

(3) Tests can be made using a small specimen.

Low cost for preparing specimen is one of important conditions for the test required a number of specimens. 3-point bending test fixture is one of general facilities for material test. It is important for general users to carry out test without special test fixture.

In contrast, the direct loading test has the following disadvantages with test procedures taken into consideration:

- (1) High cost for machining the specimens,
 - (2) Requirement of adhesive procedure, and
 - (3) Complicated procedure for confirming about measurement locations of strain gages.
 - (4) Requirement of confirmation by finite element analysis for relative thin direct loading test specimen.
- In this study, measured out-of-plane modulus with direct loading test specimens under 10mm thickness is higher than material property.

7. Concluding remarks

(1) 3-point bending tests is an available test method for evaluating the out-of-plane modulus.

(2) The ratio of bending and shear deformation affecting the out-of-plane tensile modulus using 3-point bending tests. Bending modulus close to tensile modulus as increasing L/t .

(3) It was predicted and demonstrated that the apparent bending modulus could be tensile modulus if the apparent bending modulus measured with the $L/t > 25$ bending specimen was under 15 GPa.

Fig.13 Stress-strain curves of UD-CFRP obtained by a bending test (L25mm/t1mm)

Fig.14 Stress-strain curves of UD-CFRP obtained by a bending test (L15mm/t0.5mm)

Fig.15 Stress-strain curves of UD-CFRP obtained by a bending test (L25mm/t0.5mm)

Fig.16 The bending modulus as a function of span-to-thickness ratio (L/t).

References

- [1] ASTM D 7291. In: Standard test method for through-thickness “flatwise” tensile strength and elastic modulus of a fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite material. American Society for Testing and Materials; 2007
- [2] E.HARA, T.YOKOZEKI, H.HATTA, Y.IWAHORI, and T.ISHIKAWA, Composites Part A, 41, 1538-1544, 2010.
- [3] E.HARA, T.YOKOZEKI, H.HATTA, T.ISHIKAWA, and Y.IWAHORI, Composites Part A, 41, 1425-1433, 2010.
- [4] E.HARA, T.YOKOZEKI, H.HATTA, Y.IWAHORI, T.OGASAWARA, and T.ISHIKAWA, Composites Part A, 43, 1828-1836, 2012.
- [5] SACMA SRM 4R: sacma recommended test method for tensile properties of oriented fiber-resin composites. Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association; 1994.
- [6] Advanced composites database system. JAXA-ACDB, Ver.06-1. <<http://www.jaxa-acdb.com/>>.
- [7] SACMA SRM 7R: sacma recommended test method for in plane shear stress-strain properties of oriented fiber resin composites. Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association; 1994
- [8] ASTM D 5379. Standard Test Method for Shear Properties of Composite Materials by the V-Notched Beam Method , composite materials, in-plane shear, interlaminar shear, shear modulus, shear properties, shear strength, shear testing , American Society for Testing and Materials;
- [9] C.ZWEBEN, W.S.SMITH, and M.W.WARDLE, ASTM STP 674, Composite Materials, 228-262, 1979.
- [10] ASTM D 790. Standard test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials. American Society for Testing and Materials; 2007.